

Analysis of Developments in the Understanding of In-Service Training in Turkish Public Administration: Personnel Management to Human Resource Management

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Abstract—In line with the new public management approach to provide effective and efficient services necessary to achieve the social goals of public institutions, employees must have the knowledge and skills required by the age. In conjunction with the transition from personnel management to human resources management, it is seen that there is a change in the understanding of in-service training, the understanding of "required in-service training" has switched to the understanding of "continuous in-service training". However, in terms of in-service training in Turkey, it seems to be trouble at the point of adopting to change. The main purpose of this study is to primarily create a conceptual framework of in-service training and subsequently determine, analyze and discuss the developments and problems faced by in-service training in Turkey in the transition from personnel management to human resources management. In accordance with this purpose, the necessary data of this study were collected using qualitative approaches. Observation and document analysis was used and content analysis was performed on the data gathered in the study. The results of this study, according to data such as the number of institutions requesting in-service training, allocated budget of in-service training, the number of people participating in such training, transition of personnel management to human resources management should not lead to a paradigm shift in Turkey's understanding of in-service training, although this is compulsory for public institutions in accordance with the law in Turkey. In-service training in Turkish public administration is still not implemented effectively and is seen as a social activity for employees and a formality for institutions.

Keywords—Human resources management, in-service training, personnel management, public institutions.

I. INTRODUCTION

At the present time, preferred to as the information age, together with the scientific and technological developments, both businesses and public institutes must attach importance to education in order to keep in step with the change occurring in management approach. Especially together with the approach of new public administration, public institutes should provide service effectively and efficiently to realize their social targets. This is possible through employees having the knowledge and skill level required of the era.

Although it is foreseen that the employees have a certain knowledge and skill level due to their level of education,

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improving these factors by providing in-service training offers important contributions from both personal and institutional and social points of view. Hence, in-service training is an issue having importance in terms of public administrations. This study is prepared for the purpose of analyzing the reflections of developments occurring in the approach of in-service training in Turkey. In this direction, this study will focus primarily on the definition, aim, benefits, and sorts of in-service training. Afterwards using the data of in-service training taking place in the performance programs and activity reports of State Personnel Presidency (SPP), the aim under consideration will be tried to be reached.

II. THE CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK OF IN-SERVICE TRAINING

Education, as in the other social concepts, is not a concept that can be described with an only one definition. Due to the fact that it is a process that is considered life-long and that it simultaneously incorporates political, social, cultural, and individual dimensions, there are many definitions made by dealing with the different aspects of the concept. Education, in the most general meaning, can be defined as

"the facilitating activity for new generations to gain the necessary knowledge, skills, and understanding and to develop the character and traits to prepare them for social engagement" and *"as a system of actions carried out to provide certain developments in terms of ability, character, and knowledge in human behavior"* [1].

According to another definition, education is a process to realize a change in the behaviors (knowledge, skill, habit, attitudes, etc.) of an individual in a planned way and in a desired direction [2]. In the definitions made related to education, we can say that there are two common elements [1]:

- A planned action toward previously determined aims.
- An activity and process aiming at providing development in the knowledge, skills, and aims of an individual.

Education can be divided into two areas: formal education and non-formal education. While formal education includes pre-school education, primary education, secondary education, and high education institutions, non-formal education is out of formal education and it fills any deficiency of formal education. Non-formal education is an education given to those not completing their educations or those wanting to

continue their education in subjects they need and are interested in. The elements of this system consist of public training, adult training, pre-service occupational training, and in-service training [1]. In-service training forms the basis of this study.

Raising the personnel serving in public institutes on the subjects of general culture, professional adequacy, new thoughts and methods, and developments of the relationships between institute and its environment is primarily carried out in two stages. The first of them is to educate personnel via formal education, while the second is to raise personnel in the institute, where he/she works after recruiting. This is known as "in-service training" [3]. In other words, in-service training can be defined as

"education carried out to provide the knowledge, skills, and behaviors related to their jobs to the individuals recruited to serve for a certain wage or salary in the workplaces belonging to a real and legal person" [4].

The technological developments experienced today lead to continuous change; multitudes of new information, techniques and methods, and old practices become invalid; hence, the problem arises of training talented and specialist staff to keep up with these advancements. Gaining some knowledge and skills after entering the public service increases the importance of in-service training. Beside this, in cases where measuring the knowledge and skills of public officials during recruiting is a requirement, it is important to offer the necessary training for them to gain the knowledge and skills [3].

Almost all of countries in the world, especially after 1980s, have firmly adhered to the concepts of productivity and efficiency. Governments are obliged to provide the productivity of human resources, financial resources, and the other resources, as well because meeting the increasing accountability towards their citizens whose varied desires and demands grow with every passing day; hence, the need for a well-educated labor force [6]. In-service training, at this point, integrates the labor force, one of important the actors of production process, into the other stakeholders. Thus, it provides the highest level of productivity from an institutional and the highest job satisfaction from an individual perspective [5]. There is a desire to develop and learn new things in the nature of every human. Especially business life, this desire is much more. The employees, in every stage of service, are in tendency of continuous learning and renewing oneself and, thanks to this, upgrading. In-service training presents to people the opportunity to recognize themselves and attain individual satisfaction, since his/her desires are met, he/she works more effectively in the presentation of services [7].

In-service training can be realized in the direction of many aims [3], [8]:

- Developing professional and technical knowledge: It aims at training public employees for the qualities of services they present in terms of professional and technical aspects.
- Lowering service costs by improving the productivity of public employees: The efficiency and productivity in

services is one of the main targets for public administration.

- Motivating personnel: Thanks to in-service training programs, public officials can slightly move away from the conditions of the environment, where they work and meet their resting needs and can find opportunity to develop themselves in terms of knowledge and experience.
- Preparing personnel for upper positions: It presents opportunity for a position taking place in public institute to be occupied by an employee in institute.
- Making contribution to communication between persons and departments: In-service training programs, besides raising the motivation of people from individual point of view, bringing together the employees, makes it possible group solidarity and positive development of the relationship between persons and departments.

As seen, in in-service training programs, there is a multipurpose approach. This multipurpose approach makes obligatory to well identify purposes of in-service training and act according to the plan prepared in the direction of these purposes and evaluate the results obtained [5]. In-service training programs realized in this way to provide important benefits in terms of institutes, individuals, administrators, and society.

Benefits in terms of administrators [1]:

- Since qualified employees will make fewer mistakes, administrators make supervising and monitoring easier.
- Since productivity and motivation will be high, personnel work in a harmonious atmosphere.
- Administrator is less focused on daily problems.

Benefits from an institutional perspective [9], [4]:

- It enables the quality of goods and services presented to increase.
- It enables the power of change in institute to increase and keep in step with change.
- It enables the trust of the mass served to be gained.
- It enables cooperation and communication to develop in an institute.
- It enables increased productivity and reduction in waste of resource in the institute.

Benefits from an individual perspective [9]:

- It increases the motivation and trust senses of employees.
- It enables employees to upgrade in the institutes, where they work.
- It raises the productivity of employees.
- The communication of employees with the other employees develops in the positive direction.
- It has a feature motivating the employees and increasing their respectability.

Benefits from a social perspective:

- Since an institute working effectively and efficiently will present more qualified service to the society it serves, we can say that in-service training has benefits from social points of view.

- Since the training of employees and improving their skills and qualifications also raises overall standard of society, the benefits for all can be observed.

Fig. 1 Types of in-service training

In determining the sorts of in-service training, although there are a number of classifications in the literature, those most frequently used are the classification made according to the service level of trainees, application time and place of in-service training. According to this classification, the sorts of in-service training are as follows [7]:

- *In-service training according to service level of trainees*
 - a) Probationary training: It is a sort of training given to the candidate personnel newly entering or participating in professional life. It provides adaptation training for new personnel to the duties they will undertake, and generally has two sub categories, as orientation training and internship training. The target in orientation training is to present the institute where the new recruits will serve, the profession and role they will execute, and introduces colleagues, as well as teaching the rights, duties and responsibilities of public officials. Internship training can also be given to the candidates in the public service. Internship training involves equipping new recruits with the basic knowledge, skills, and experience the job requires and giving them opportunity to use adapt to professional life [7], [2].
 - b) Development training: In this kind of training, what is under consideration is to develop the public service personnel in parallel with the developments experienced related to their own domains. Because the developments in the science and technology, continuously affect the organizations and methods, it brings together with changes of ways, methods, equipment, information, etc. Therefore, organizations desiring its personnel to produce more qualified, productive, and high-quality goods and services have to give training for employees timely and continuously, following the developments concerned with their field or sector [2].
 - c) Promotion training: It is a sort of in-service training, organized to fill the top level positions the institute needs,

and offers an opportunity for ambitious and successful employees to advance in their position and career by acquiring the qualities and competencies required for more senior positions [9].

- d) Career training: In this kind of training, also known as supplementary education, a training activity is organized for personnel whose role and position is changed for various reasons, and allows them to gain the competencies required for the new position [2].
- *In-service training according to application time*
 - a) On-the-job training: It is a sort of training aimed at developing personnel while carrying out their duties and is generally applied to new recruits. In this sort of training, the employee learns the tasks required by their position by doing; in other words, work and training is intertwined [10]. In this training, the tasks the employee will perform are outlined, the expectations are described and the employee slowly starts in their role. In this process, a trainer is available to monitor and provide support to help bring new employees to the desired skill and qualification level.
 - b) Off-the-job training: This sort of training can be realized in two ways, as “trainings realized within institute but off-the-job” and “programs enabling employees to utilize educational opportunities out of the institute” [11]. In training carried out in the institute but off-the-job, educational activities are carried out by utilizing the facilities of the institute and its building and equipment. That trainer will generally come from outside of the institute. The decision of whether to provide “off-the-job training” on-site or not is generally associated with the budget and facilities available. The option that is the most suitable for institutions should be chosen [12].
 - *In-service training according to field of application*
 - a) In-service on-site training: This training focuses on specific problems or areas for improvement within a department or organization. The training program is attended by a homogenous group due to the fact that those participating in training are the personnel of the institute. These trainings carried out at the institute provide important benefits to employees in solving existing problems. On the other hand, in in-service training which is carried out on-site requires personnel to be absent from their posts for a certain period of time, thus, it can also be motivating. On-site trainings are relatively cheap, while being highly beneficial [13].
 - b) In-service off-site training: In the sort of training performed out off-site, in contrast to on-site, there is a non-homogenous group those attending come from various institutions. Rather than discussing institute-specific problems, at the point of increasing the knowledge and skills of employees, creating an environment for mutual discussion is also a way for employees to improve their capacities and broaden their scope. In addition, in-service training organized off-site allows employees to focus on the training and to network. Off-site training allows personnel to discuss and produce

new ideas objectively because are able to disconnect from the day-to-day distractions of the office environment. Training programs which are conducted off-site can be more useful compared to those held on-site [13].

III. FROM PERSONNEL MANAGEMENT TO HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT: CHANGES IN THE IN-SERVICE TRAINING

In today's rapidly changing world organizations are obliged to adapt and modernize by bringing themselves up-to-date and in line with new processes and technologies. The developments experienced in the scientific, social, and technological areas have led to the emergence of a new approach to human resources management due to the fact that personnel adapt to the demands of modern management [14]. Human resources management is perceived as a modern concept replacing personnel management, in fact, the transition concerned is a process that considers long-term change. Thus, human resources management is an approach presenting significant differences from personnel management, and can be summarized as follows:

TABLE I
 DIFFERENCES BETWEEN PERSONNEL MANAGEMENT AND HUMAN RESOURCES MANAGEMENT [31]

DIMENSION	PERSONNEL MANAGEMENT	HUMAN RESOURCES MANAGEMENT
Detection of Human Life	Life of the individual is fragmented (business and private).	The life of the individual as a whole.
Monitoring and Evaluation	External control, labor standards, performance measures, finds errors and winnow out.	Internal control, guidance of group, prevention and guidance of errors.
Service Mentality and Targets	Human is for the organization.	Organization is for the human.
Position of Human	Present position is the basis.	It is an active process.
Motivation Tools	Mainly financial rewards.	Mainly moral rewards.
Discipline	Strident and punishment.	Towards prevention.
In-Service Training	In-service training if necessary.	Continuous on-the-job and off-the-job training.
Management Style	One-way and sanctions oriented.	Participation and cooperation-oriented.
Vision and Mission	Organizations and individuals focus on different goals.	Organizations and individuals focus on the same goals.
Criteria of Efficiency	Performance.	Performance and feedback.
Decision on Personnel	It is important what they do and know.	It is important what they can do and how their competency level.
Selection and Recruitment	Personnel according to work.	Work according to personnel.
Development	Developing individual skills consistent with the job.	Developing individual skills as a whole.
Ultimate goal	Productivity, profits.	Individual happiness and social welfare.
Scope	From recruitment to dismissal.	From recruitment to dismissal, and beyond.

Table I shows how human resources management, as an approach, includes aspects of classic personnel management however moves beyond the concept, qualifying an employee as "equity capital" by removing the "passive" element, as well

as giving importance to the behavioral dimension such as motivation of employees, social agreement, and the happiness of the individual [3]. Therefore, in human resources management, employees are the most important resource, which must be developed and invested in. Continuous training, viewed as a cost element in personnel management, has become the main policy of all organizations with human resources management [3].

The new duties, which have economic, social, and technical content and stand out in the framework of the new public administration approach, require that individual departments and institutions as a whole function well, and employees make sound economic and rational decisions. It has become important to employ and train qualified employees for public administration, whose competencies and scope of skills and experience, gradually expand. In the process of social change and industrialization, ensuring public officials adapt to changing conditions, and develop the necessary competencies to offer effective service has become some of the main functions of public administrations. At this point of performing this function, in-service training is viewed as the most important instrument in providing efficiency and effectiveness in terms of the competencies of public service personnel [15]. Hence, the approach of "occupational in-service training, if necessary" that was present in personnel management has been replaced with the approach of "Continuous on-the-job training and off-the-job training" and focuses on the development of individual as a whole, rather than developing the qualifications of an individual applicable to a specific role. At the same time, as also seen in Table I, emphasis has shifted away from what personnel currently know, to their capacity in terms of long-term competencies.

IV. AN OVERVIEW OF IN-SERVICE TRAINING IN TURKEY

When examining the economies of many developed countries, the importance given to education and the level investment in personnel training, is noteworthy. Countries such as Germany, Japan, and the US have a highly productive economic structure which they largely owe to successful implementation of in-service training activities [16]. In most of developed countries, in-service training is given the necessary attention, providing a greater level of support for training and developing employees, as it is seen as a long-term investment [17]. For example, in the United Kingdom, between 1989 and 1990, the government invested £381 million, or 6% of the overall budget, on training of public officials. That is an average of £788 spent for training each public servant [18]. As another example in most developed countries, a budget, which is the equivalent of around 1% of a teacher's annual salary, is allocated for career training and development. In Turkey, however, the Ministry of National Education allocates a budget of between 16TL to 20TL in-service education, depending on their years of services and less than 0.1% of a teacher's salary [19], [20].

To understand the function of Turkish public administration and to assess the failure of in-service training to change and develop, it is first important to grasp the legal basis of in-

service training, while looking at intra-institute training units as well as units of in-service training in institutes. Finally, this paper will identify the problems and barriers that limit the direction, understanding and implementation of in-service training in Turkish institutions.

A. Legal Basis of In-Service Training in Turkey

In Turkey, in-service training in public institutes and organizations is a necessity and required by law. The basic law on this subject is the Public Servants Law (PSL), No. 657. In 55th item of the law concerned, the expressions that “It is stipulated that “All public servants assigned as candidate are first subjected to training related to their common attributes then, to preparatory training related to their domains and internship. And also, if candidates become successful they are assigned as public servant”; that “The basic training and preparatory training are carried out in the same institute”; and that “Training times, programs, and bases of evaluations will be carried out and under the responsibility of which institutes and/or other points that are determined by a regulation prepared by the Prime Ministry” take place. According to Item 56, “The relations of those being unsuccessful in each of the basic and preparatory training and internship periods in the candidateship process with the civil service are broken off”. As is also understood from this item, in the stage of candidateship, in-service training, basic training, preparatory training, and internship training are obligatory. The activity of basic training is given to a person to attain the common qualities of public servants. In preparatory training, considering the public servant occupies position and duty, the knowledge required by his/her role and duty is given. In internship training, in the light of theoretical knowledge acquired in preparatory training, this enables a public servant to gain experience by applying the knowledge and skills learned.

In the items on “training public servants” taken place in Part 7 of PSL, the expressions in the form that “In-service training to be applied, in order to enable public servants to become qualified, increase their productivity, and prepare them the further positions, carried out according to the regulations, which will be prepared by the State Personnel Presidency together with the relevant institutes” and that “In each institute, a training unit is established for arranging, carrying out, and assessing the training activities. In institutes in which more than one unit is established, one of these is called the Central Training Unit.

In Item 217, titled the “General Plan of Training of Public Servants”, for dealing with in-service training in the public sector using a holistic approach and to realize an established system, it was foreseen that the “Training General Plan of Public Servants” is formed by a decree from Ministerial Board. This plan is prepared by the Personnel Department of Prime Ministry taking into consideration the views of the Ministry of Finance, National Ministry of Education, Ministry of Youth and Sports, TODAIE/IPATME (Institute of Public Administration for Turkey and Middle East), State Planning Organization, and the relevant institutes and put into operation

by the decree of the Ministerial Board. Thus, in order to meet the idiosyncratic requirements of institutes, a level of independence was recognized, and in the plan, two sorts of training are foreseen, which are pre-service and in-service [21], [22].

The subject of in-service training was also included in the country’s five-year development plans. Especially, after the 1960s (together with planned period), studies toward improving the quality of human resources gained importance. In 1st five-year development plan, which came into force in 1963, and considering the economic, social, and cultural aspect of development, it was emphasized that education was one of the most important instruments of development. It expressed that the way of raising the values of order, desired to be reached, and of creating the personal and group behaviors to direct society to the target, occurs through education [23]. Due to that fact that those raised in educational institutes do not have the desired qualifications and that many people are employed out of the occupations they are trained for, the importance of in-service training was underlined and was said that only thanks to this, the necessary quality and productivity could be obtained [23].

In 2nd five-year development plan, in-service training was included under the title “General Education” and the expression that “it is necessary to increase work productivity and raise the quality of services” was given. In the plan, it was suggested that despite applications continuing for long time about in-service education, an effective system was not established and that public and private organizations and employers did not adopt the responsibility of methodical and systemic training. And also in this plan, the importance of the Public Administration Institute for Turkey and Middle East (TODAİE) was emphasized [24]. Similarly, also in another five-year development plan, the objection of increasing the efficiency of personnel together with in-service training was extensively addressed. However, to what degree this aim could be reached remains problematic, as each five-year development plan contains an evaluation of the previous plan and includes the negative statement that “the desired targets were not reached” [1].

B. In-Service Training Organizations in Turkey

In Turkey, in-service training activities have to be legally realized by the relevant institutes and organizations. In every institute, a training unit to carry out in-service training applications is established, made obligatory by law. According to Item 215 of the public servants law, in-service training is organized, executed, and evaluated by the training units or training center established by the institutes themselves. However, being responsible for in-service training of public officials, there are some institutes providing inter-institute in-service training, and providing coordination for in-service training [17], [2]. Although the National Productivity Center, Industrial Education Development Center and the Near and Middle East Study Center are among the institutes concerned with in-service training, in the following section, the importance of these two institutes in regard to in-service

training at the macro level in Turkish Public Administration is briefly discussed.

- a) *Institute of Public Administration for Turkey and Middle East (IPATME)*: The first important organization related to the training of public servants of the central administration is IPATME. IPATME, achieved public status in 1959 under the umbrella of Faculty of Political Sciences based on the agreement made with the United Nation Technical Aid Department in 1952 [1]. In Turkey, since the application of in-service training is carried out in two ways, inter-institute and intra-institute. The inter-institute dimension of in-service training is carried out by IPATME, which is the relevant institute of the Ministry of Employment and Social Security and has financial autonomy and a legal personality. IPATME organizes training programs in the form of short-term courses and seminars in administrative areas at the institutions and organizations, as well as provides post graduate and doctorate education in the area of public administration. And with regard to senior public servants and promotions, IPATME also carries out in-service training programs, both short and long duration [21].
- b) *State Personnel Presidency (SPP)*: Public Servants Law No. 657 assigned some duties related to training and promoting public servants at the State Personnel Department, which was established under Law No. 160 in 1960. The SPP was established in order to determine the methods and means for personnel to be prepared and promoted to higher positions. Law No. 160 was amended by statutory decree in 1984. The amendment declared among the first items that the duty to conduct pre-service and in-service trainings of public officials was one of the aims of the presidency. Among the duties of the presidency, the 3rd item of the law, which relates to training, states that “developing the necessary programs related to preparing, applying, following, and assessing the appropriate training programs and supervising applications in this area in order to allow personnel planning in public institutions, as well as assist in applying it and enabling personnel at each stage to be trained and promoted in-service, as well as to be prepared for the further positions” and that “conducting the necessary coordination and program development works to reflect the subjects that are useful for advancing the qualifications, knowledge, and practices related to the duties required by public servants in pre-service training programs” were given place [6]. The Presidency of Educational Affairs was established under the authority of the SPP in order to oversee the training activities conducted by state institutions. According to legislation, the SPP are also responsible for overseeing the coordination, identifying educational policies, and controlling polices related educational activities among public institutions [1].

C. Problems of In-Service Training in Turkey and Constant Understanding of In-Service Training

After 1980, the Turkish Public Administration signed a number of economic reforms under the influence of neo-liberal policies. In managerial terms after the 2000s, reorganization studies were initiated in the areas of local government, fiscal management and audits, and administration of public personnel, to enable the direction and approach of the new public administration. One of the focuses of the new public administration was to reform key principles such as efficiency, productivity, accountability, transparency, result oriented, performance management, decentralization, horizontal organization, quality, competition, policy forming, planning, and service presentation in Turkey, with the introduction of the Public Fiscal Administration and Control Law No. 5018 [25]. In light of the principles of accountability and fiscal transparency, the law targeted more effective, economical and efficient use of public resources. In accordance with item 9 of the relevant law related to public institutions, “the obligation to prepare performance programs and measures that include the activities that will be undertaken, the resource needs, targets and performance indicators” was imposed. In this direction, the performance programs issued by the State Personnel Presidency are some of the important data resources for in-service training in recent years. Figs. 2 (a)-(d) show the targets related to in-service training in the performance programs published by the State Personnel Presidency.

Fig. 2 (a) In-service training in state personnel department's performance programs (2008-2015) [28]-[30], [32]

Fig. 2 (b) In-service training in state personnel department's performance programs (2008-2015) [28]-[30], [32]

Fig. 2 (c) In-service training in state personnel department's performance programs (2008-2015) [28]-[30], [32]

Fig. 2 (d) In-service training in state personnel department's performance programs (2008-2015) [28]-[30], [32]

One of the key aims determined in the Strategic Plan of the State Personnel Presidency for the years 2003-2017, is "to

raise the quality of public sector personnel by arranging in-service activities more effectively". Another strategic aim is "to arrange general personnel in the public regime according to needs within the framework of modern human resources management, and in accordance with service requirements and determined productivity principles." The importance of the transition from personnel management to human resource management was also emphasized in the introduction of the 2009-2013 strategic plan published by the SPP. However, when taking into consideration the data shown in Figs. 2 (a)-(d) in terms of in-service training, which is an important factor in human resource management, the situation in Turkey does not appear positive. While it was determined there would be a significant increase in the number of institutes demanding in-service training, as shown in Fig. 2 (b), on the other hand, it is predicted that there would be a decrease in the number of training programs organized.

As shown in Fig. 2 (d), the estimated financial resources required for in-service training increased in 2015, and is based on the expected rise in the number of institutions demanding in-service training. The predicted resource needs for in-service training increased to TL 518,000 in 2015, up from TL 160,000 in 2011. An increase of 47, 210 was recorded in the number of institutions demanding in-service training in respect to the same years. However, it is not accurate to interpret the rise in demand for in-service training as a shift towards the adoption of training practices in Turkey. It is worth noting the decline in the number of in-service training programs conducted with respect to these years, despite the increase in demand for training, as shown in Fig. 2 (b). Meanwhile, no significant changes were recorded in the number of personnel participating in in-service training and the number of assigned trainers, as shown in Fig. 2 (c). As well, no significant change was recorded in regard to the number of personnel and in the preparation and update of in-service training course notes for the same years, as shown in Fig. 2 (a).

TABLE II
2015 ANNUAL REPORT OF STATE PERSONNEL DEPARTMENT [33]

INDICATORS OF PERFORMANCE	2015 TARGET	ACTUAL	DEVIATION FROM TARGET (%)
The number of institutions demand for in-service training	210	120	-42.85
The number of organized in-service training programs	6	36	+500
The number of trained personnel and trainers	3,700	1,411	-61.86
The number of prepared and updated notes about in-service training	140	321	+129.28
The number of personnel trained abroad	710	794	+11.83
The number of Council of Ministers' decision draft about in-service training	3	3	0
The number of concerns answered regarding in-service training for personnel, institutions and organizations	830	410	-50.6
The number of inspected draft and training programs	520	352	-32.30

According to the 2015 Annual Report of State Personnel Presidency, (see Table II), significant deviation was recorded from the targets established for the performance indicators for programs related to in-service training.

Although the report shows a substantial increase in the number of in-service training programs organized in 2015, it is worth highlighting that the number people benefiting from this training fell well short of the target, and represents a negative deviation of 61.86%. A significant negative deviation from the target was also recorded for “the number of concerns answered regarding in-service training for personnel, institutions and organizations” and “the training programs and drafts examined”.

As seen in the above figures in regard to in-service training starting from 2008, when no a serious deviation was recorded from the targets, it can be said that the existing situation is not satisfactory and reveals serious deviations from the in-service training targets set. According to the 2015 Annual Report of the State Personnel Presidency, the absence of inter-institution training and a congress center is one of the important weaknesses. Other deficiencies and issues of in-service training in Turkey can be listed as follows [26], [27], [2], [20]:

- Since the certificates bestowed to the participants as a result of in-service training activities are not effective in assigning, shifting and upgrading, the participation in these activities decreases.
- In most institutions, due to the fact that work analyses are carried out to determine duty requirements and there are no clear job descriptions, the degree of in-service training programs focused on functional aims is problematic.
- Training environments are inadequate. Most institutions do not have modern training instruments and technologies, and hence, most training is only for show.
- There are no course notes or auxiliary instruments that will assist in the instruction of the in-service training process or they have only a superficial quality.
- Serious difficulties are experienced in measuring the success levels of those participating in in-service training programs and the degree of test questions used for this aim is questionable.
- Top level managers remain uninterested in in-service training in institutions.
- The budget allocated to in-service training is constrained and investments made in education centers and equipment for training is inadequate.
- At the point of making decisions on in-service training, the element that is taken into consideration is the decision of the central administration rather than local needs.
- In-service training activities are evaluated as holiday or social activity by employees.
- Employees are of the opinion that the staff members participating in in-service training programs are incompetent.
- In-service training programs are focused on occupational themes and fail to train individuals on topics such as human relationships and work safety.

- An understanding of the necessity to provide continuous in-service training, not because it is considered mandatory, was brought in institutions.

Due to the issues previously mentioned, a clear reflection of the developments experienced in the approach of in-service training to Turkish public administration is not possible. In-service training is viewed as a formality by institutions. Hence, it can be said that from the viewpoint of Turkish public opinion, in-service training is not at the adequate level and that with the approach of new public management, the changes experienced in the concept of in-service training in the direction of the transition from personnel management to human resources management is problematic in Turkey.

V.CONCLUSION

Due to the technological and scientific developments experienced at the present day, the traditional management culture not responding the needs of time was left and replaced with a modern management culture. The change occurring in management approach also showed itself in personnel management and transition to human resources management became an obligation and necessity. Together with the change of interest, management approach that was previously work-oriented left its place to human-oriented approach. The employees have been viewed as the most important resources, on which making investment is necessary. Although substituting the other resources can be possible, due to the fact that substitution of qualified labor force, who directs the work he/she carries out rather than performing his/her duty, is difficult, the prioritized target of the institutions had been to continuously raise its employees in service with a holistic approach.

In Turkey, in-service training is necessity in public institutions and organizations as requirement of laws. However, although this state seems to be positive, due to the lowness of the budget allocated to in-service training, absence of qualified trainers, and limitedness of the degree of assessments which are made at the end of training, to serve aim, and not using assessments made in/at favor or expense of employees, and many problems deficiencies that are existent, the process does not affectively functions. However, generally, in-service training is perceived as a formality that is necessary to be performed by the institutions and social activity in terms of the employees. Hence, although solving the problems and removing deficiencies are important steps for Turkey, they do not seem to be enough. What is important is to recognize that the transition from personnel management to human resources management does not result from a nomenclature problem and that it is a change of approach and to change mindset.

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